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Research Article

The Role of Word Content, Sentence Information, and Vocoding for Voice Cue Perception

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: For voice perception, two voice cues, the fundamental frequency (f_0) and/or vocal tract length (VTL), seem to largely contribute to identification of voices and speaker characteristics. Acoustic content related to these voice cues is altered in cochlear implant transmitted speech, rendering voice perception difficult for the implant user. In everyday listening, there could be some facilitation from top-down compensatory mechanisms such as from use of linguistic content. Recently, we have shown a lexical content benefit on just-noticeable differences (JNDs) in VTL perception, which was not affected by vocoding. Whether this observed benefit relates to lexicality or phonemic content and whether additional sentence information can affect voice cue perception as well were investigated in this study.

Method: This study examined lexical benefit on VTL perception, by comparing words, time-reversed words, and nonwords, to investigate the contribution of lexical (words vs. nonwords) or phonetic (nonwords vs. reversed words) information. In addition, we investigated the effect of amount of speech (auditory) information on f_0 and VTL voice cue perception, by comparing words to sentences. In both experiments, nonvocoded and vocoded auditory stimuli were presented.

Results: The outcomes showed a replication of the detrimental effect reversed words have on VTL perception. Smaller JNDs were shown for stimuli containing lexical and/or phonemic information. Experiment 2 showed a benefit in processing full sentences compared to single words in both f_0 and VTL perception. In both experiments, there was an effect of vocoding, which only interacted with sentence information for f_0 .

Conclusions: In addition to previous findings suggesting a lexical benefit, the current results show, more specifically, that lexical and phonemic information improves VTL perception. f_0 and VTL perception benefits from more sentence information compared to words. These results indicate that cochlear implant users may be able to partially compensate for voice cue perception difficulties by relying on the linguistic content and rich acoustic cues of everyday speech.

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The ability to perceived differences between the voices of speakers can be of big help during speech perception. Two voice cues, fundamental frequency (f_0) and vocal tract length (VTL), seem to contribute the most to

the perception of voice and speaker characteristics (Darwin et al., 2003; Skuk & Schweinberger, 2014; Vestergaard et al., 2011). Because of spectrotemporal degradations inherent to cochlear implant (CI) electric stimulation of the auditory nerve (for a review, please see Başkent, Gaudrain, et al., 2016), users of CIs have difficulties in perceiving the two voice cues, showing higher discrimination thresholds for f_0 and VTL compared to normal-hearing (NH)

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listeners (Gaudrain & Başkent, 2018; Zaltz et al., 2018). When compared to simulation studies where the spectrotemporal resolution was degraded by means of vocoding, similar results were shown for some vocoding settings (Gaudrain & Başkent, 2015). These deficits in voice cue sensitivity can directly explain abnormal voice gender categorization among CI users (Fu et al., 2005; Fuller et al., 2014; Massida et al., 2013; Meister et al., 2016), as these two voice cues are also used for this task. Furthermore, difficulties in other voice-related tasks have also been observed in CI users, such as perception of prosody (for a review, see Everhardt et al., 2020), vocal emotions (e.g., Jiam et al., 2017), indexical cues (e.g., Tamati & Moberly, 2022), and identification of talkers (for a review, see Colby & Orena, 2022). However, it is less clear how specifically the perception of average f_0 and VTL may relate to these tasks.

Most studies on voice cue perception in CI listeners use simple speech materials, such as isolated syllables or words, for better control of the conditions and simplicity in study design. In everyday listening, however, speech communication provides richer speech cues, with longer speech segments and more linguistic content (e.g., lexical and sentential context). Spectrotemporal degradation of the speech signal in electric hearing can make distinguishing between differences in voice cues or linguistic cues ambiguous. To solve this ambiguity, CI users need to rely on top-down compensatory mechanisms for correct interpretation of the degraded speech cues (Amichetti et al., 2018; Başkent, Clarke, et al., 2016; Nagels et al., 2020; Winn & Moore, 2018). This was evidenced by studies showing that CI users can use linguistic context to make lexical decisions (Gianakas & Winn, 2019; Nagels et al., 2020). It is possible that similar compensatory mechanisms could also be employed for voice perception.

In a recent study (Koelewijn et al., 2021), we aimed to investigate the effect of top-down compensatory mechanisms, related to word (lexical) content, on voice cue discriminability. We assessed the effect of lexical content on just-noticeable differences (JNDs) in f_0 and VTL and their combination ($f_0 + \text{VTL}$) for normal and vocoded speech, using an auditory adaptive odd-one-out task (three-interval, three-alternative forced choice). In this study, NH participants listened to meaningful Dutch consonant-vowel-consonant (CVC) words that were presented forward or time reversed. While time reversing prevented lexical access (Ptacek & Sander, 1966), talker-specific voice cues, such as f_0 and VTL and the acoustic entropy, were preserved. This way, the amount of lexical/semantic information available was manipulated orthogonally from the acoustic voice cues. In addition, during each trial, either the same word was repeated 3 times (low-variability context) or three different words were presented (high-variability context), whereas in

both cases, one of the three items was uttered with a deviant voice. The results showed that within the context of high variability, when presented with forward words, participants showed smaller VTL JNDs compared to time-reversed words. These outcomes suggest that lexical content may help to resolve ambiguity in whether a difference between items could be related to voice or to phonetic information, an ambiguity that primarily occurred in the variable condition when the phonetic content differed across intervals and when the acoustic features of the VTL voice cue and phonetic content overlapped. This result did not change when vocoding was applied. For f_0 JNDs only in the nonvocoded condition with low variability, this lexical content benefit (forward words vs. time-reversed words) was shown.

In a follow-up study performed by Jebens et al. (2022), the effect of lexical content on f_0 and VTL voice cue discriminability was further investigated using a voice gender categorization task, this time by making the distinct separation between lexicality (word meaning) and phonological (though phonetic alterations) effects. Lexicality was investigated by comparing word to nonword cue weights (outcomes) and phonological effects by comparing nonword to time-reversed nonword cue weights of the voice gender categorization task. This showed lower (worse) cue weights for time-reversed nonwords compared to forward nonwords and words but no difference in cue weights between words and nonwords, suggesting voice gender categorization to be affected by phonological rather than lexicality effects. These outcomes (Jebens et al., 2022) raised the question of whether the observed effect in our previous study (Koelewijn et al., 2021) relates to what we in this study will refer to as “lexical information” (whether a word exists in the lexicon) or “phonemic information” (associated with phonological content including coarticulations within words) as part of the linguistic content available in words. In addition, it made us wonder whether additional speech (auditory) information available in sentences (in addition to the linguistic content of the individual words) like sentential content (semantic), sentential context, and coarticulation between words compared to single words (a factor we will call “sentence information”) could affect voice cue perception.

A study by Meister et al. (2016) tested CI users and NH listeners for speaker voice gender categorization in single words and sentence stimuli. Findings from this study revealed that changing the f_0 and VTL voice cues combined ($f_0 + \text{VTL}$) had a more substantial influence on the speaker’s gender perception for NH listeners than changing only the f_0 voice cue. NH listeners relied on both f_0 and VTL because these cues conflict when manipulated singularly. On the other hand, CI users showed ambiguous responses for speaker gender recognition,

which can be explained by the limited spectral resolution of CI devices, affecting the ability to detect VTL differences (also see Fuller et al., 2014). Besides, they found that performance in sentences was better than single words or four-word sequences in both groups, which might be explained by having more information in sentences that allows for more detailed analysis. However, CI listeners did not make use of VTL cues regardless of stimulus type. Whether a similar sentence benefit will be observed at the level of voice cue discrimination and also whether VTL JNDs would improve by full sentence processing are unknown.

What we do know is that speech contains both linguistic and indexical information (Abercrombie, 1967), which seems to interact in a way that processing word or phoneme information can improve our sensitivity to voice cue differences (Koelewijn et al., 2021). This is in line with previous studies that already showed this link between linguistic and indexical information in speech perception (Nygaard, 2008; Pisoni, 1997). By time reversing speech, most lexical content especially semantic information (word meaning) can no longer be retrieved, resulting in words that sound unfamiliar as they do not occur naturally in reversed form. According to Binder et al. (2000), in reversed speech, some phonetic features that are temporally symmetrical (fricatives and vowels) may be preserved. However, plosive consonants, because of their strong abrupt onset and a more gradual decay, are most likely not preserved when this signal is time reversed. In addition, coarticulations are reversed and therefore may sound unfamiliar. This means that the part of the lexical content benefit observed previously by Koelewijn et al. (2021) could, in addition to the absence of word meaning, be attributed to disrupted processing phonemic information (e.g., consonants) in reversed speech. Hence, our previous study only using words and reversed words could not dissociate between the negative effect of reversed speech on VTL voice cue discriminability, being related to lexical information, phonemic information, or both.

Experiment 1: Lexical Content

The first experiment expanded on the characterization of potential lexical content benefit effect previously observed on VTL perception (Koelewijn et al., 2021), by comparing words, time-reversed words, and nonwords, presented in both nonvocalized and vocalized versions. The lexical content benefit, referring to the participants' ability to detect smaller changes in the VTL voice cue for words compared to time-reversed words, could be related to lexical information and/or phonemic information. There is a difference between real words, nonwords, and reversed words based on phonological and lexical components

(Jebens et al., 2022). Words have both phonemic and lexical information that facilitates recognition. Nonwords only obey the phonological constraints of a natural language but contain no lexical information. The time-reversed words, as was used by Koelewijn et al. (2021), do not follow the Dutch language's phonological constraints and do not carry information to be represented in the mental lexicon. We hypothesized that spoken word recognition involves phonological and lexical components that facilitate lexical retrieval. Therefore, smallest JNDs were predicted with words followed by nonwords and reversed words, respectively. Any significant difference in JNDs between real words and nonwords would signal the distinct representation of real words in the mental lexicon. In line with Koelewijn et al. (2021), we expect larger VTL JNDs for the vocalized conditions and no interaction with word type.

Method

Participants

Of the 23 participants that initially signed up, 21 started the online experiment. A total of 14 participants performed all adaptive runs of the online experiment, of which three participants were excluded due to producing unusable data in some runs. Data from the remaining 11 participants (self-reported gender: six women and five men, age range: 22–41 years, $M_{\text{age}} = 29$ years) were analyzed. Additional demographics were collected to further describe the participant population. It is not clear at this point, based on literature, if any of these factors may or may not affect voice perception with or without vocalizing, but for the purpose of completeness, we provide these demographic details. From the 11 participants, two reported MBO (secondary vocational education), one reported HBO (higher vocational education), and eight reported university-level education (according to the Dutch schooling system); all reported to have learned two or more languages in addition to their first language (three learned three additional languages, two learned four additional languages); no participant was reported to be raised bilingual; five participants played a music instrument of which three received formal music education before the age of 10 years; one participant reported to speak with a regional accent; and four participants lived 1 year or more outside the Netherlands. All participants reported NH and normal or corrected-to-normal vision. Participants did not report dyslexia, epilepsy, and/or history of developmental disorders. They all were native Dutch speakers and provided written informed consent in accordance with the Ethics Committee of the University Medical Center Groningen (METc 2018/427). Participation was voluntary, meaning that

participants received no monetary compensation. Participants were recruited via word of mouth at the University of Groningen and the University Medical Center Groningen.

Stimuli

Three sets of audio stimulus items used contained words, nonwords, and time-reversed words. Each set consisted of 75 stimuli, and the Dutch words and nonwords were selected from the VariaNTS corpus (Arts et al., 2021). The VariaNTS corpus contains 11 linguistic categories based on lexical frequency, phonotactic probability, and neighborhood density. The selected words had a high frequency and low density (easy words), and the nonwords had a low phonotactic probability and high density (hard nonwords). Phonotactic probability refers to the frequency of occurrence of combinations of phones in language. Nonwords with a low phonotactic probability do still follow these language rules but are less common. The terms “easy” and “hard” in the VariaNTS corpus refer to the processing demands of the linguistic information. Easy words and hard nonwords were selected to maximize the difference in effect they might have on VTL JNDs. The VariaNTS corpus contains recordings of eight female and eight male native talkers of standard Dutch. The audio files selected for this experiment were from a 20-year-old native Dutch female NH speaker with no regional accent, a height of 171 cm, a weight of 59 kg, and with an average f_0 of 214.36 Hz. The time-reversed word items were created in Adobe Audition (Version 2020) by time reversing the audio files of the set word items.

Voice cue changes were processed online with WORLD (Morise et al., 2016). For more details on voice cue manipulation, see Gaudrain and Başkent (2015, 2018) and Supplemental Materials S1 and S2. In the adaptive procedure described below, VTL of the stimuli was varied in each trial. Three randomly selected stimuli were resynthesized with WORLD using the new VTL parameter, and word duration was normalized to 600 ms. The stimuli were resynthesized even when the VTL was unchanged compared to the original voice.

The auditory stimuli were presented without and with vocoding. Vocoding was coded in Python (as part of the VTServer Version 2.2; Gaudrain, 2021), in line with a previous implementation in MATLAB (Başkent, Gaudrain, et al., 2016; Gaudrain & Başkent, 2015), and ran in real time on a dedicated online sound processing server. In line with our previous study (Koelewijn et al., 2021), we used a vocoder simulating low spread of excitation (LS-vocoder) and a vocoder simulating high spread of excitation (HS-vocoder). Both vocoding conditions used 12 analysis filters. These were 12th-order (72 dB/oct.) zero-phase Butterworth filters with a range spanning from 150 to 7000 Hz, which were

uniformly divided in terms of cochlear place of excitation (Greenwood, 1990). For the LS-vocoding condition, the synthesis filters were identical to the analysis filters, whereas for the HS-vocoding condition, fourth-order filters (24 dB/oct.) were used. The temporal envelope was extracted, in each frequency band, by half-wave rectification and low-pass filtering. These low-pass filters (zero-phase fourth-order Butterworth) had an effective cutoff frequency of half the bandwidth of each band, with a maximum of 300 Hz (Gaudrain & Başkent, 2015). For both vocoding conditions, noise was used as a carrier signal.

Procedure

Participants performed a three-alternative forced-choice (3AFC) task. During each trial, three consecutive stimuli items were presented, and participants chose the one that sounded different relative to the other two. Although they could use any cue available to choose the odd one out, depending on the specific experiment and/or condition, the “voice cue” manipulated was VTL only. Note that the content of each of the three items was different, which entail variability in acoustic content, phonological content, and lexical content for words.

For each condition, JNDs were estimated separately using a 2-down-1-up staircase procedure (Levitt, 1971), resulting in approximately 71% correct response for each test (adaptive run). For each adaptive run, the VTL of the deviant item started at a 12-semitones (st) absolute distance from the female reference voice of the other two items. Each adaptive run started with a 2-st step size, which reduced by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ every 15 trials or when the voice difference became smaller than twice the step size. The test ended after eight reversals, after 150 trials, or when it reached a difference of 25 st, and the JND was calculated as the mean over the last six reversals and the difference that would have been presented in the following trial. If eight reversals were not reached in 150 trials or the staircase reached a difference of 25 st, the procedure was aborted, and the data were unusable.

In the 3AFC task, participants had to select the odd one out based on any perceivable voice difference. During each trial, participants listened to the three items play in sequence, while at the same time, the three corresponding buttons, presented on screen from left to right, briefly lighted up. Participants responded by a mouse click on the button corresponding to what they perceived as the deviant item. At the end of each trial, they received visual feedback from the selected button by blinking in green or red for correct or incorrect responses, respectively. Each condition was presented in a block-wise fashion of which the order was randomized separately for each participant.

Online Testing and Apparatus

For running the experiment online, a platform was developed by the dB SPL research group within the University Medical Center Groningen. The platform was coded in JavaScript using the jPsych library (Version 6.2; de Leeuw, 2015) and was accessible through a web browser. Participants were advised to run the experiment on a desktop or laptop computer, to use a good set of headphones, and to perform the experiment in a quiet environment. The experiment started with general project information about the hearing research conducted in our lab, followed by an informed consent form, to which participants had to agree before they could continue. Next, participants had to fill out an online questionnaire containing questions on demographics relevant for voice and speech perception research. Subsequently, participants received experiment-specific instructions, adjusted the sound levels presented through their headphones to a comfortable level, followed by a short practice session before the start of the actual experiment.

Statistical Analysis

All JNDs were log-transformed to improve homogeneity of variance across conditions. We performed a 3×3 repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) on the log-transformed VTL JNDs with lexical content (forward, reversed, nonword) and vocoding (no, low spread [LS], high spread [HS]) as the within-subject factors. Effect sizes are reported as generalized eta squared (Bakeman, 2005). For planned comparisons on the data of Experiment 1, paired-samples t tests were used. The Holm–Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons (Holm, 1979) was used, and adjusted p values are reported. Effect sizes for these t tests are reported as Cohen's d . The statistics were computed in R Version 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2020) with the ez package Version 4.4.0 (Lawrence, 2016) using Type III sums of squares.

Results

The outcome showed a significant main effect of vocoder, $F(2, 20) = 68.0$, $p < .001$, $\eta_g^2 = .65$, and a significant effect of word status, $F(2, 20) = 22.0$, $p < .001$, $\eta_g^2 = .21$, on VTL JNDs (see Figure 1). However, there was no significant interaction, $F(4, 40) = 0.80$, $p = .479$, $\eta_g^2 = .02$. For planned comparisons between word status conditions, the thresholds were averaged over all vocoder conditions. Three paired-samples t tests were used for comparing JNDs between the word status conditions. A significant difference was found between words and reversed words,

$t(10) = -5.83$, $p_{\text{adj.}} < .001$, $d = 1.76$, showing larger (worse) JNDs for reversed words compared to words. Also, nonwords and reversed words were significantly different from each other, $t(10) = 5.15$, $p_{\text{adj.}} < .001$, $d = 1.55$, showing larger JNDs for reversed words compared to nonwords. The words and nonwords were also significantly different, $t(10) = -2.43$, $p_{\text{adj.}} = .035$, $d = 0.73$, but note that the effect size was only moderate. These results showed that both lexical and more phonological information was associated with smaller (better) JNDs. Additionally, for planned comparisons between vocoder conditions, the thresholds were averaged over all word status conditions. Three paired-samples t tests were used for comparing JNDs between the vocoder conditions. The results were significantly different between the no vocoder and LS-vocoder, $t(10) = -8.45$, $p_{\text{adj.}} < .001$, $d = 2.55$, and between the no vocoder and the HS-vocoder, $t(10) = -9.59$, $p_{\text{adj.}} < .001$, $d = 2.89$. Finally, the two vocoders were also found to be significantly different, $t(10) = -2.47$, $p_{\text{adj.}} < .05$, $d = 0.74$, but note that the effect size was only moderate.

Discussion

The results of Experiment 1 show that, in line with our hypotheses, the lexical content benefit as observed previously, when presenting variable items (Koelewijn et al., 2021), is related to lexical information available in words and phonological content available in both words and nonwords. In our previous study (Koelewijn et al., 2021), presenting variable items across the three alternatives resulted in larger VTL JNDs compared to presenting the same item (fixed) 3 times. This is because, for the fixed items conditions, variations in formant frequencies between items were only related to shifts in VTL, which made these differences stand out. In contrast, in the variable condition, different CVC words were presented, each potentially containing different vowels that would additionally contribute to formant variation. Only the variable item conditions showed a benefit of lexical content, suggesting that word content, only available in forward speech, helped to disambiguate between differences in formants related to either shifts in VTL or variable word items. The current results now specifically showed a lexical and phonological benefit in VTL discriminability. The latter is explained by change in transients, resulting in, for instance, the absence of plosives in consonants and affected coarticulations in time-reversed speech. Note that vowels and fricatives are preserved in time-reversed speech (Binder et al., 2000). This was revealed by comparing the three conditions: words that contain both lexical and phonological content, nonwords that have no lexical but full phonological content, and time-reversed words that have

Figure 1. Median JNDs on the y-axis (log-spaced) for each lexical content (forward, reversed, and nonword), vocoding (no, LS, and HS), and voice cue (VTL) condition. Boxes extend from the lower to the upper quartile (the interquartile range, IQ), and the midline indicates the median. The whiskers indicate the highest and lowest values no greater than 1.5 times the IQ, and the dots indicate the outliers (i.e., data points larger than 1.5 times the IQ). HS = high spread; JNDs = just-noticeable differences; LS = low spread; Rev = reversed; VTL = vocal tract length.

no lexical and impoverished phonological content. In other words, it seems that the absence of lexical information, and of plosives and coarticulations, affecting phoneme processing, resulted in a significant decrease in VTL discriminability. Note that this study did not investigate the effect of lexical content on f_0 JNDs but focused on VTL sensitivity instead. This is because, in our previous study (Koelewijn et al., 2021), only VTL JNDs were affected by lexical content when vocoded, which may indicate that top-down compensatory mechanisms can improve voice perception.

In line with the outcomes from our previous study (Koelewijn et al., 2021), the observed semantic and phonological benefit on VTL perception was shown for both vocoder conditions. This suggests the possibility that CI users could rely on phonological content to compensate for the difficulties in perceiving VTL, as shown by Gaudrain and Başkent (2018), and using it for voice gender recognition, as shown by Fuller et al. (2014). On the one hand, it might be that some of these previous studies only using syllables, instead of meaningful words or sentences (e.g., Zaltz et al., 2018), underestimated VTL discrimination in CI users. On the other hand, it is known that access to phonological content in CI users is often hampered when it comes to perceiving steady-state vowels (Fielden et al., 2015). Vowel perception in general is difficult for CI users since they cannot easily distinguish the voiced cues of harmonic structure or hear spectral peaks, and they confuse place cues (Fu et al., 1998). Dynamic cues are easier to hear by CI users because cues move and the transition of a peak from one electrode to another would make it more audible, but steady vowels do not provide this. However, contradicting evidence is also shown (Donaldson et al., 2015). Still, as discussed earlier, it is most likely the plosives in

consonants and coarticulations that are affected by the reversal of the speech signal. Hence, the current results indicate a possibility for better VTL perception in CI users when it comes to real-life listening situations than what is measured in lab experiments with short speech segments or syllables.

Experiment 2: Words Versus Sentences

Experiment 1 shows that lexical and phonemic content in words had an influence on VTL JNDs. In Experiment 2, we look at the effect of adding additional sentence information (content, context, and coarticulation) by comparing JNDs with single words to full sentences. Nonvocoded as well as vocoded speech was presented, as full sentence processing was previously observed to have an effect on voice gender categorization in CI listeners (Meister et al., 2016). Since HS-vocoding conditions in Experiment 1 were shown to be very difficult, even resulting in unusable data for some of the participants, in Experiment 2, only LS-vocoding was implemented. Both f_0 and VTL voice cues were independently manipulated since CI users, in that same study, as well as others (e.g., Fuller et al., 2014), seemed only to make use of f_0 voice cue differences. The pitch contours (e.g., f_0) are more complex in sentences than single words and therefore might contribute to the detectability of voice differences. Experiment 2 addressed the question of whether additional speech (acoustic, lexical, and/or semantic) information conveyed through sentences compared to words influences the participant's ability of discriminating voice cues (f_0 and VTL). We predicted smaller JNDs in both f_0 and VTL voice cues when sentences are presented compared

to words. Again, in line with Koelewijn et al. (2021), we expect larger JNDs for the vocoded conditions.

Method

Participants

Of the 13 participants that signed up and started the online experiment, a total of 12 participants performed all adaptive runs, of which one participant was excluded due to producing unusable data in some runs. For the remaining 11 participants (self-reported gender: eight women and three men, age range: 26–52 years, $M_{\text{age}} = 32$ years), the data were analyzed. Additional demographics collected are the following. From the 11 participants, one reported HAVO (senior general secondary), one reported HBO (higher vocational education), and nine reported university-level education; all reported to have learned two or more languages in addition to their first language (seven learned three additional languages, one learned four additional languages); one participant reported to be raised bilingual (Dutch and English); three participants played an instrument of which one received formal music education before the age of 10 years; one participant reported to speak with a regional accent; and seven participants lived 1 year or more outside the Netherlands. All participants reported NH and normal or corrected-to-normal vision. Participants did not report dyslexia, epilepsy, and/or history of developmental disorders. They all were native Dutch speakers and provided written informed consent in accordance with the Ethics Committee of the University Medical Center Groningen (METc 2018/427). Participation was voluntary, meaning that participants received no monetary compensation. Participants were recruited via word of mouth at the University of Groningen and the University Medical Center Groningen.

Stimuli

The stimuli consisted of audio words and sentences. For sentence stimuli, the original recordings of Dutch everyday sentences from the VU98 corpus by a native Dutch female talker (referred to as talker HB) were used (for a full description, see Versfeld et al., 2000). For word stimuli, 28 Dutch meaningful CVC words, part of the Nederlandse Vereniging voor Audiologie corpus (Bosman & Smoorenburg, 1995), were extracted from the original recordings of the VU98 corpus. In that way, resulting word and sentence stimuli were uttered by the same female talker (HB) with an average f_0 of 175 Hz.

Voice cue changes were processed online with WORLD (Morise et al., 2016) the same way as in

Experiment 1 (see Supplemental Materials S1 and S2). Three randomly selected stimuli were resynthesized with WORLD using the new f_0 and/or VTL parameters. The stimuli were resynthesized even when the f_0 and/or VTL was unchanged compared to the original voice. The auditory stimuli were presented without and with noise vocoding. Experiment 2 only used the LS-vocoding condition, and all settings were the same as in Experiment 1.

Procedure

Experiment 2 was again run online the same as Experiment 1. Participants performed a similar 3AFC task as described previously. Each adaptive run started with a 12-st difference and a 2-st step size for each voice cue, which reduced by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ every 15 trials or when the voice difference became smaller than twice the step size. Again, the content of each of the three items was different, which entail variability in sentence content and context. For each condition, JNDs were estimated separately similarly as in Experiment 1.

Statistical Analysis

All JNDs were log-transformed to improve homogeneity of variance across conditions. In line with our previous research (Koelewijn et al., 2021), data for each voice cue were separately analyzed, since intersubject variance tends to be different for f_0 and VTL. Hence, for each of the voice cues, we performed a separate 2×2 ANOVA on the log-transformed JNDs with sentence information (words, sentences) and vocoding (no, LS) as the within-subject factors. For post hoc analysis, paired-samples t tests were used. The Holm–Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons (Holm, 1979) was applied. ANOVAs were performed in R Version 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2020) with the ez package Version 4.4.0 (Lawrence, 2016) using Type III sums of squares. Effect sizes are reported as generalized eta squared (Bakeman, 2005).

Results

The outcomes (see Figure 2) for f_0 JNDs showed a significant main effect of sentence information, $F(1, 10) = 8.70$, $p = .015$, $\eta_g^2 = .23$, and vocoder, $F(1, 10) = 175$, $p < .001$, $\eta_g^2 = .68$. There was a significant interaction between vocoder and sentence information, $F(1, 10) = 7.13$, $p = .023$, $\eta_g^2 = .06$, but note that the effect is small. Post hoc analysis in the form of two separate pairwise t tests showed a significant difference between words and sentences in the nonvocoded conditions, $t(10) = -3.34$, $p_{\text{adj.}} = .015$,

Figure 2. Median JNDs on the y-axis (log-spaced) for each lexical content (words and sentences), vocoding (no and LS), and voice cue (f_o and VTL) condition. Boxes extend from the lower to the upper quartile (the interquartile range, IQ), and the midline indicates the median. The whiskers indicate the highest and lowest values no greater than 1.5 times the IQ, and the dots indicate the outliers (i.e., data points larger than 1.5 times the IQ). JNDs = just-noticeable differences; LS = low spread; VTL = vocal tract length.

$d = 1.01$, but not for the vocoded conditions, $t(10) = -1.72$, $p_{\text{adj.}} = .117$, $d = 0.52$.

The outcomes for VTL JNDs showed a significant main effect of sentence information, $F(1, 10) = 17.9$, $p < .01$, $\eta_g^2 = .30$, and vocoder, $F(1, 10) = 74.8$, $p < .001$, $\eta_g^2 = .41$. However, there was no significant interaction between vocoder and sentence information, $F(1, 10) = 0.04$, $p = .85$, $\eta_g^2 < .01$. Planned comparisons in the form of two separate pairwise t tests showed a significant difference between words and sentences in both the nonvocoded conditions, $t(10) = -3.90$, $p_{\text{adj.}} < .01$, $d = 1.17$, and the vocoded conditions, $t(10) = -2.41$, $p < .05$, $d = 0.73$.

Discussion

The results of Experiment 2 suggest that more speech information by presenting sentences compared to words improved the discriminability of both f_o and VTL voice cues, with the exception of the f_o vocoded condition. More information available in sentences, in one form or another, means more variability in the signal. This might be reflected by more f_o fluctuations, and that probably means more formant fluctuations too, which would make the detection of mean differences between f_o or VTL voice cues more difficult. However, this account assumes that the cues are simply accumulated over time without any effect of sentence information. Linguistic content would also provide interpretability or even predictability of the content. Meister et al. (2016) investigated the effect of both stimulus length and sentence information (semantic content) on voice gender categorization in NH and CI users while systematically manipulating f_o and VTL cues. To independently manipulate the effect of stimulus duration and

amount of sentential context, a single word (0.4–0.5 s), a sequence of four unrelated words (quadruple, approximately 2 s), and simple sentences (mean length = 1.7 s) were presented. The quadruple provided acoustic variation comparable to a sentence but without the predictability of pitch contour and intonation, without coarticulatory cues of naturally produced sentences, and without the semantic information and sentential context normally available in a sentence. Their results showed larger differences between the results for f_o -VTL and f_o voice cue for sentences compared to quadruples, indicating effects of sentence information (content, context, and coarticulation), and again compared to single words, indicating effects of stimuli duration (number of words), on voice gender categorization. Hence, the results of this study likely show the same combined effect on JNDs in f_o and VTL cues. Apart from a possible effect of stimulus length, presenting sentences within this task increases the amount of linguistic information available to the listener at phoneme, word, and sentence levels. Findings from the literature suggest that this additional linguistic input can be used in a top-down manner to improve speech perception (e.g., Bashford & Warren, 1979; Başkent, 2012; Meister et al., 2009, 2016, p. 201; Verschuure & Brocaar, 1983; Warren, 1970) and also for cognitive compensation of degraded speech (Başkent, Clarke, et al., 2016) as shown for VTL JNDs.

For CI users, this sentence benefit might be specifically beneficial, as they have a higher reliance on context information (Dingemanse & Goedegebure, 2019), though other studies showed that how much these listeners profited varied greatly across different CI users, while often the processing effort increased (Wagner et al., 2019). Still, there are several aspects to which sentences are different from words. Sentences vary with respect to several

linguistic aspects compared to words. Not only are they longer and contain more acoustic cues, but they also contain semantic information in the form of context, have higher lexical content, and show more phonetic aspects, such as intonation and coarticulations. Solely comparing sentences with words therefore leaves the question of which of the linguistic aspects adds to which part of the measured benefit. Although these outcomes do not give us a definitive answer to this question, it shows the listener's ability to use this additional information to their advantage.

General Discussion

In this study, we aimed to investigate the effect of top-down compensatory mechanisms related to lexical word content (lexical and phonemic) and sentence information (content, context, and coarticulations) on voice cue discriminability. In addition to previous findings (Koelewijn et al., 2021), the results of Experiment 1 show more specifically that semantic content available in words and phonological content available in both words and nonwords improves VTL perception relative to time-reversed words. These results are partly in line with Jebens et al. (2022), who did observe an effect of phonological content but not of lexical content on use of voice cues in voice gender categorization. The outcomes of Experiment 2 were as predicted by showing smaller f_0 and VTL JNDs when sentences were presented compared to words, except for the f_0 vocoded condition where no difference between JNDs was shown. This indicates that voice cue perception benefits from more speech (auditory) information, like sentential content (semantic), sentential context, and coarticulation between words, available in sentences compared to single words. This is in addition to the linguistic content of the individual words that make up the sentence (Meister et al., 2016). Importantly, these results were shown with and without vocoding, which has implications for CI listening as discussed below.

Compensation for Degradations Caused by Vocoding

As hypothesized, both experiments showed larger JNDs for the vocoded conditions compared to the nonvocoded conditions. In Experiment 1, both LS- and HS-vocoders were used to mimic observed differences in spread of excitation by CI electric stimulation of the auditory nerve (for a detailed explanation, see Başkent, Gaudrain, et al., 2016). The results show a main effect of vocoding and no interaction with word status, which is in line with previous outcomes (Koelewijn et al., 2021). The benefit of lexical and phonemic information on VTL

JNDs was shown even for the most degraded HS-vocoder condition. In Experiment 2, where only an LS-vocoder was implemented, a sentence information benefit was shown for the vocoded VTL voice cue condition but not for the vocoded f_0 voice cue condition. Both experiments show a benefit on VTL voice cue perception for the vocoder conditions. In line with our previous study (Koelewijn et al., 2021), this suggests that CI users could resort to top-down mechanisms relying on linguistic content like phonemes, words, or full sentence context as a compensatory strategy (Başkent, Clarke, et al., 2016).

Overall Implications for CI Users

The current results have some potential general implications for CI users. Until now, most research using syllable sequences (e.g., CV triplets) or single words showed that CI listeners (El Boghdady et al., 2019, 2021; Gaudrain & Başkent, 2018; Nogueira et al., 2021), or NH listeners tested with vocoders (El Boghdady et al., 2018; Gaudrain & Başkent, 2015), have difficulty hearing VTL voice cues. Furthermore, CI users or vocoder-tested NH participants make voice gender categorization that differs from that of NH listeners, in how they are using VTL voice cues. In vocoder simulations, more random answers are given than a systematic misuse of f_0 or VTL voice cues, whereas CI users show a systematic overreliance on f_0 while making no use of VTL. The results from Experiment 2 show that when presenting sentences, either due to being a longer signal and presenting more acoustic cues related to voice, both CI/vocoded and NH listeners can make use of rich linguistic and semantic content, and this may help to better perceive VTL voice cues. In line with this, Meister et al. (2020) conclude that CI listeners can use timbre cues (related to VTL) when presented with sentences instead of CVC or single-word stimuli, a result also shown by Zaltz et al. (2018), although affected by age of implantation, using short three-word sentences. This may mean that in real life, CI listeners may be able to hear and make use of VTL voice cues, when listening to a conversation. Still, we need to keep in mind that these results are observed with vocoded speech presented to NH listeners. Although a vocoder provides some degradation implemented in a way that resembles some of the CI signal processing and, when vocoder parameters are carefully selected, can provide a good overlap in results from simulations and CI users (Gaudrain & Başkent, 2015, 2018), there is still no guarantee that this degradation is a good representation of real CI listening for this specific study. The current results based on vocoded speech only imply that with sentences, NH listeners can compensate for some degradation of voice cues compared to syllables. In CI users, there are other elements that may play a role, such

as damage to the auditory nerve, where the electrodes are located, and limitations of electric hearing, but also long-term adaptation to the CI transmitted sounds. Importantly, the study by Meister et al. (2016) does show an effect of using sentences compared to words in voice gender categorization with CI users, which supports the idea that the current results might be replicable by a future study with actual CI users.

Conclusions

This study extends our previous findings (Koelewijn et al., 2021) by similarly showing an interaction between voice perception and the acoustic and linguistic content of the stimuli. However, further than the previous study, the results show that the interaction between lexical content and voice perception is specifically related to phonemes available in words and nonwords compared to time-reversed words. Word meaning does not show a significant benefit on VTL perception. In addition, results suggest that linguistic relationships provided by sentences improve voice discrimination. Interestingly, both the phonological and sentence content advantage were resilient to signal degradation by means of vocoding. These outcomes suggest that top-down mechanisms depending on lexical and phonemic information available in words and sentence information, likely a combination of semantic content, context, and acoustic cues like coarticulations between words (Meister et al., 2016), could potentially be utilized as a compensatory strategy by CI listeners (Başkent, Clarke, et al., 2016).

Data Availability Statement

The data sets generated during and/or analyzed during this study are available in the DataverseNL repository: <https://doi.org/10.34894/JPGDMN>.

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